

PROBLEMS AND NEEDS OF TEACHING THE ENGLISH LANGUAGE IN THE UZBEK AUDIENCE

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ABSTRACT

The article deals with the main problems that students studying English in different countries of the world, and especially in Iran, face in the learning process. The article aims to acquaint readers with specific difficulties in teaching the English language, suggests options for solving these problems, methods for improving the quality of education in training centers.

“The only way that to some extent can guarantee students success in actively mastering one or another foreign language and avoiding the danger of mixed bilingualism is the way of conscious repulsion from their native language: students must learn any new difficult phenomenon of a foreign language through its comparison with the phenomenon of the native language corresponding in meaning” [1, p. 57]. When a person begins to learn a new, non-native language, he first of all notices the formal differences between this language and his native language. In cases where the concepts of the native and studied languages coincide, such a correlation helps learning, speeds it up. However, in most cases there are discrepancies that cause the so-called interference, when the student transfers the concepts of the grammar of the native language into English [2].

Differences in the systems of different languages require the selection of those grammatical concepts of the English language that will be new for students. In a comparative study of linguistic phenomena, a foreign researcher cannot but take into account the interference of his native language. Attention to interference when teaching a foreign language, first of all, helps teachers to notice which language issues are mastered with great difficulty, in which cases the interference stimulates and where, on the contrary, it slows down the acquisition of a foreign language.

Taking into account or exclusion of the native language of students when teaching foreign languages is still a controversial methodological issue, and the decision in which direction to compare: from native to English or from English to native is considered the main one. The principle of taking into account the native language in the methodology of teaching a foreign

language has different interpretations [3, p. 61].

Some methodologists (O. D. Mitrofanova, V. G. Kostomarov) suggest, when selecting linguistic phenomena, to proceed from the system of the studied, and not the native language. This makes it possible to systematically select, minimize, organize and present educational material, i.e. solve the main strategic issues of mastering another language. The specificity of the native language, in their opinion, is not a criterion for building a course of the language being studied [4, p. 110–112].

“Taking into account the native language as a category of science of methodology is drawn as the most rational and effective set of methods for teaching this educational material in relation to a certain national language environment in its arrangement dictated by the logic of the language being studied, presentation and consolidation of the facts of the studied language”. [4, p. 70]. Other methodologists (for example, E. M. Motina and G. I. Rozhkova) believe that the native language should be considered as a determining factor in the selection of material on the English language, in the sequence of its presentation, in the dosage and forms of work on it. The native language is necessary in determining the most difficult to assimilate linguistic phenomena of a foreign language for students of a particular nationality, which largely affects the construction of a training program and the creation of a system of specific exercises [5].

Problems and needs of teaching the English language in the Uzbek audience: The third group of specialists (A. A. Leontiev, I. A. Zimnyaya) understands the native language as a factor that determines what can and should be transferred from the native

language of students, what can and should be corrected that enter as a completely new, unknown. Then linguistic phenomena are singled out that can be compared for methodological purposes, and it is proposed to identify the features of incomplete coincidence or complete divergence of languages, since the assimilation of these processes manifests the interfering influence of the speech system of the native language as more developed and firmly rooted in consciousness and speech activity on the newly formed communicative system of a foreign language [6].

There are researchers who believe that the most important thing when learning a foreign language is the strict separation of both language systems, that successful mastery of a foreign language can only be achieved if the systems of the native and foreign languages contact with each other as little as possible. [4].

English and Uzbek doesn't belong to the same Indo-European language family. Thus, their grammatical systems are quite different. Some discrepancies and inconsistencies between these two languages are associated with problems:

1) the absence in the Uzbek language of such English grammatical categories as aspect, and 2) the differences of some categories from Uzbek (gender category). So, for example, due to the absence of the aspect category in many languages, when explaining this category, the teacher is practically deprived of the opportunity to rely on the students' native language or intermediary language. The theory and practice of teaching English as a foreign language show that numerous errors in the use of verb types are explained by the complexity of the characteristics of the action in the English language and their

difference from the characteristics of the action in the Uzbek language, therefore, when teaching the English language, the vision of the cognizable linguistic features of English of the native language through the prism of the native language and relying on this vision during the educational process.

The teacher must, firstly, find all the possibilities that facilitate the understanding of this material, and, secondly, on the one hand, acquaint students with these differences on the basis of knowledge of their native language, and on the other hand, encourage them to speak and think only in the target language, taking into account these differences.

So, the teacher will properly develop the speech skills of students. Thus, we can say that when teaching the category of a species, an experienced teacher should:

- form in students a certain concept of the category of the species and its relationship with the categories of time, modality and aspectuality;

- establish the relationship between the grammatical forms of the perfect and imperfect form and the meanings they convey;

- emphasize the close interaction of the lexical and grammatical meaning of the aspect in the verbal lexeme; - distinguish and explain cases where it is possible or impossible to replace perfective verbs with imperfective verbs and vice versa;

- determine the contextual conditions for the manifestation of specific meanings and teach students to identify the contextual indicators of a particular specific meaning and find their correspondence in their native language;

- explain the influence on the use of aspectual forms in a certain context, which is exerted by the communicative intentions

of the speaker, and to explain the behavior of perfect and imperfect verbs in texts of various types and styles.

Often strong students use some part of the study time inefficiently, lack the attention of the teacher, losing their advantages [8, p. 63], and they get bored because the teacher involuntarily focuses on average students and even on the level below the average. The teacher must involve all students in the work in accordance with their level of knowledge and skills and divide them into appropriate groups. Several weak students should participate in each group, and the teacher can ask the strong ones to help the weak students during the lesson. Thus, the strong will feel more useful and will no longer be bored, there will be closer and more friendly interaction between students. The teacher should use several means and methods at the same time and gradually choose those that are most suitable for his students.

Recently, various methods have been widely used for more effective teaching of the English language. In the course of testing different methods, it is found that, on the basis of the best method, it is necessary to pay attention to the psychological state of students, the choice of suitable teaching material, the development of students' speech and the variety of types of work in the classroom. In the future, choosing the right teaching method not only allows you to significantly speed up the learning process and reduce time costs, but also provides an opportunity for students and teachers to get the best result at the end of the training. It should be said that developing all types of speech activity in students, teaching students to clearly and correctly express their thoughts and communicate with native speakers is much

more difficult and more important than teaching them only language as a system. Since our goal is to develop communication and prepare a person for life and work in society, then, first of all, we need to: 1) understand what the problem is when studying and teaching English as a foreign language;

2) develop knowledge in the field of teaching the English language and get

acquainted with the methodology of teaching foreign students this language;

3) improve "new" skills and implement the proposed methods in teaching the English language;

4) take into account the structure of education in order to solve the problems of teaching foreigners a non-native language.

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